

Otoro Nuba

Data source: eHRAF

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** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: African Religions, Religious Group

The term Nuba refers to over 50 distinct ethnic groups residing in the Nuba Hills of what is now Sudan (Adem, 2019:1). Otoro refers to a particular Nuba tribe that occupies the Otoro Hills hill chain. This entry focuses on the Otoro Nuba during the 1930s, and relies primarily on ethnographic information from principal ethnographic authority Siegfried Frederick Nadel. Nadel conducted fieldwork with the Nuba from 1938-1941, during which time the region was under British control as part of the Anglo-Egyptian Sudan. While the Otoro had come into contact with European cultures and the primarily Muslim and Arabic population of the surrounding area, European and Islamic influences on the Otoro at the time of Nadel's fieldwork were limited. At this time, the Otoro lived in eight separate hill communities, each containing many homesteads or small villages. The Otoro were organized into 35 patrilineal and strictly exogamous clans, ranging in size from 20 to 130 families (Nadel, 1947:92). An age grade system was also utilized: at puberty, Otoro males were assigned to an age-based group and collectively underwent initiation rituals that created strong social bonds. At the time of Nadel's writing, the Otoro were developing a system of chieftainship. Each hill of the Otoro Hills had a separate chief with the skills necessary to interact with external bureaucratic entities. Religious leaders included priests with various specialties, such as the rain-maker or the grain priest. The Otoro rituals and ceremonies centered largely around the agricultural calendar and the life cycle. Although not described in substantial ethnographic detail, supernatural beings were identified as being present in the form of previously human spirits. For the Otoro, religious beliefs were inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life. Therefore, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large.

Date Range: 1910 CE - 1945 CE

Region: Nuba Hills Otoro, ca. 1930

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Sudan

Nuba Hills Otoro, ca. 1930

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fj21-001>

– Source 1 Description: Nadel, S. F. (Siegfried Frederick). 1947. *The Nuba: An Anthropological Study of the Hill Tribes in Kordofan*. London: Oxford University Press.

– Source 2 URL: <https://d-place.org>

– Source 2 Description: Kathryn R. Kirby, Russell D. Gray, Simon J. Greenhill, Fiona M. Jordan, Stephanie Gomes-Ng, Hans-Jörg Bibiko, Damián E. Blasi, Carlos A. Botero, Claire Bown, Carol R. Ember, Dan Leehr, Bobbi S. Low, Joe McCarter, William Divale, and Michael C. Gavin. 2016. D-PLACE: A Global Database of Cultural, Linguistic and Environmental Diversity. *PLoS ONE*, 11(7): e0158391. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0158391.

– Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fj21-000>

– Source 3 Description: Adem, Teferi Abate. 2019. "Culture Summary: Nuba." New Haven: Human Relations Area Files.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Otoro tribe of the Nuba has come into contact with Islamic cultures, but this contact has had limited effects on Otoro culture. See Nadel, 1947:483-485 for more information.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: "It [the scarcity of iron in the Nuba Mountains] is essentially a result of the difficult intertribal relations, the permanent state of suspicion and active hostility that existed between the different Nuba tribes and between Nuba and Arabs" (Nadel, 1947:70).

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: "This is the most up-to-date method [of bringing an unknown criminal to justice]: certain persons possess powerful charms, bought from itinerant Arab or West African charm-sellers, which are reputed to kill evil doers." (Nadel, 1947:156). See also Nadel, 1947:163 for an image of Arab road shops.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), "Internal warfare seems to occur every year, but usually only during a particular season" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), "External warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Membership is consequently assumed to be assigned at birth.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Therefore, it is assumed that the religion has political support.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: "There is no indication that Otoro chieftainship was ever linked with a religious dignity, save, for a time, with the half-religious office of the Master of Ceremonies in the triennial age-grade ritual" (Nadel, 1947:165).

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: "No other features of the traditional culture have been embodied in this modern chieftainship. Only one of the Otoro sub-chiefs holds a religious office as well (Sheikh Karim of Kujur-Nworre, who is also the local grain priest). The Sheikh of Urila, Gyarge, is the son of the rain-maker and has himself for a time acted as such; but his magic failed, and he ceded the religious office to his younger brother" (Nadel, 1947:170).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 40000

Notes: "The Otoro, the largest tribe in the Eastern Jebels (numbering about 40,000), inhabit a far-flung hill range composed of eight main hill chains." (Nadel 1947:86).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The religious congregations which recognize the spiritual leadership of a common priest are essentially local groups, composed of people who live together and—above all—farm together on the

same territory. The stretch of land belonging traditionally to a local community is thought of as being in the spiritual care of its 'grain priest.'" (Nadel, 1947:45).

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Every member of a given clan has the potential to develop that clan's associated powers or qualities. Priests always possess these powers. See Nadel, 1947:95 for more information.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: Every member of a given hereditary clan has the potential to develop that clan's associated powers or qualities. See Nadel, 1947:95 for more information.

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: Powers of the religious leader are unique to the position they assume. See Nadel, 1947:45, 163 for more information.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: Religious leadership appears to be hereditary: "There existed a special hereditary office in Otoro and Tira, the kwelen kweti tat, the 'Chief of the Path', who acted as intermediary in these peace negotiations" (Nadel, 1947:159). Nadel, 1947:163 indicates that grain priests were also hereditary.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: "In the case of a young, inexperienced priest—or an ancient priest who is no longer in full possession of his faculties—the old men would not rely on his judgement, but would themselves take the initiative and warn their priest that the time for this or that sacrifice had come" (Nadel, 1947:45).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 66, Large or Impressive Structures, there are no large or impressive structures present among the Otoro Nuba [Murdock and Wilson, 1972; retrieved from D-PLACE (Kirby et al., 2016)].

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for different types of religious architecture.

↳ Tombs:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of tombs. Rather, evidence indicates that the deceased were buried on a funeral hill (Nadel, 1947:323).

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: See Nadel, 1947:323 for an image of a funeral hill. For further discussion of burial practices see Nadel, 1947:95-96.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: "It is tempting to speculate on the psychological readjustment which these changes of locality [forced by the British government] must have entailed: a religion based on the presence of sacred places and centres of worship in the midst of the people, suddenly turned into a cult whose shrines, far away from the scenes of daily life, become remote objects and sites of pilgrimage" (Nadel, 1947:6)

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: See Nadel, 1947:163 for image of Urila Hill and a shrine for fertility rites.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Forced relocation by the British government resulted in sacred places and shrines becoming places of pilgrimage (Nadel, 1947:6).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Personhood continues in the form of a potentially jealous spirit that can survive after the death of the body (Nadel, 1947:120).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: After death, personhood continues in the form of a spirit, suggesting the spirit is ontologically distinct from the body (see Nadel, 1947:120 for more information).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: After death, personhood continues in the form of a spirit, suggesting the spirit is ontologically distinct from the body (see Nadel, 1947:120 for more information).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "For the spirit of the dead hunter is believed to take his trophies with him into the other world and, thus equipped, to lay claim there to the spirits of all the animals which he had killed in his life on earth" (Nadel, 1947:59). Belief in an afterlife is indicated, but not described in detail.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: The deceased are typically buried (Nadel, 1947:95-96). See questions below for more information.

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of cremation. Rather, evidence indicates that adherents are interred. See Nadel, 1947:95-96 for more information.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of mummification. Rather, evidence indicates adherents were interred. See Nadel, 1947:95-96 for more information.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "In the burials of Heiban and Otoro the direction in which the head of the body is placed varies in accordance with the clan to which the dead belonged" (Nadel, 1947:95-96).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– I don't know

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– I don't know

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Notes: Because the head of the body is oriented in the direction of the clan, it is assumed that the deceased are not buried upright: "In the burials of Heiban and Otoro the direction in which the head of the body is placed varies in accordance with the clan to which the dead belonged" (Nadel, 1947:95-96).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of cannibalism. Rather, evidence indicates adherents were interred. See Nadel, 1947:95-96 for more information.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates exposure to the elements. Rather, evidence indicates adherents were interred. See Nadel, 1947:95-96 for more information.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of feeding to animals. Rather, evidence indicates adherents were interred. See Nadel, 1947:95-96 for more information.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale, secondary contact with the remains of the deceased does not occur (Schroeder, 2001; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale, secondary contact with the remains of the deceased does not occur (Schroeder, 2001; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the deceased are buried with grave goods. See questions below for more details.

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence implies that women are buried with some personal items: "Her household utensils and personal belongings (so far as they are not buried with her or placed on her grave) go to her daughters or—failing daughters—sisters" (Nadel, 1947:130).

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Notes: "When the hunter himself dies, these trophies are placed on his grave, For the spirit of the dead hunter is believed to take his trophies with him into the other world and, thus equipped, to lay claim there to the spirits of all the animals which he had killed in his life on earth" (Nadel, 1947:59).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: See Nadel, 1947:323 for an image of a funeral hill. For further discussion of burial practices see Nadel, 1947:95-96.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: See Nadel, 1947:323 for an image of a funeral hill.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of tombs. Rather, evidence indicates that the deceased were buried on a funeral hill (Nadel, 1947:323).

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of domestic burials; evidence indicates adherents were buried on a "funeral hill" (Nadel, 1947:323).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are present in the form of previously human spirits (Nadel, 1947:120).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of a supreme high god.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "[In the case of marriage to a widow] There is no marriage ceremonial, but a certain ritual must be performed before the consummation of the marriage, to placate the spirit of the dead husband" (Nadel, 1947:120). Ethnographic evidence indicates that previously human spirits are present, however, they are not described in substantial detail.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "[In the case of marriage to a widow] There is no marriage ceremonial, but a certain ritual must be performed before the consummation of the marriage, to placate the spirit of the dead husband" (Nadel, 1947:120).

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Notes: Ethnographic evidence describes supernatural beings that have deliberate causal efficacy in the world, but not whether these supernatural beings were previously human (Nadel, 1947:44).

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: "When the hunter himself dies, these trophies are placed on his grave, For the spirit of the dead hunter is believed to take his trophies with him into the other world and, thus equipped, to lay claim there to the spirits of all the animals which he had killed in his life on earth" (Nadel, 1947:59).

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: "The faeces of the sacrificial animal are food for the spirit of the dead, as are also the bits of meat, especially liver, kidneys, and entrails, which will be smeared on a tree or rock when the people sit down to the meal that concludes this rite" (Nadel, 1947:120).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– I don't know

Notes: Based on the following ethnographic information, it is not clear what type of supernatural being these grain-dwelling spirits are: "The rational motive of avoiding distraction during this most busy period appears in the guise of superstitious fears: the fear that singing or shouting would stop the growth of the grain, or that the spirits which are said to dwell in the growing grain would attack revellers" (Nadel, 1947:44).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information is available regarding supernatural monitoring (for the time and place focus of the present entry).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information is available regarding supernatural punishment (for the time and place focus of the present entry).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information is available regarding supernatural rewards (for the time and place focus of the present entry).

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. General social norms of the Otoro are thus applicable to the religious group: "Morality is carried by the social institutions; it is confirmed by every traditional procedure and demonstrated, implicitly, by every religions ceremony. It is demonstrated more specifically by the various organizations of adolescence, and impressed upon the growing generation by the example and the teaching of their elders" (Nadel, 1947:511).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: "Sex morality—marital and pre-marital—is extremely lax" (Nadel, 1947:119).

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: "Neither prayers nor fasts have as yet found their way into Nuba life" (Nadel, 1947:485).

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: For descriptions of food avoidances, see Nadel, 1947:98-99, 520.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: Permanent scarring is not explicitly mandated for membership, but remains important: "The association of cicatrization with a test of manhood is emphasized in various ways. The very cicatrization pattern is thought of as a symbol of manly virtues. Men who killed an enemy in a fight are entitled to have a small pattern of scars (four to seven rows) cicatrized on their backs" (Nadel, 1947:142).

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Sacrifice is not explicitly mandated for membership, but remains important: "But the dissipation [of accumulated wealth] may be brought about by two widely different methods. One represents essentially a transfer of wealth (e.g. in bride-price and kinship gifts), the other a destruction of wealth (through sacrifices and slaughtering) . . . In Otoro, Heiban, Koalib (the 'bull tribes') and Tira the aspect of 'destruction' predominates" (Nadel, 1947:67).

Destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: "But the dissipation [of accumulated wealth] may be brought about by two widely different methods. One represents essentially a transfer of wealth (e.g. in bride-price and kinship gifts), the other a destruction of wealth (through sacrifices and slaughtering). Although the two methods occur side by side in all Nuba tribes, they are employed in a characteristically varying proportion in different groups. In Otoro, Heiban, Koalib (the 'bull tribes') and Tira the aspect of 'destruction' predominates" (Nadel, 1947:67).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: "Neither prayers nor fasts have as yet found their way into Nuba life" (Nadel, 1947:485).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Notes: Rituals are described in limited ethnographic detail: "Certain trophies, over and above proclaiming the hunter's skill, gain almost ritual significance. Every time a man kills an antelope he will take the hooves and shoulder blades, tie them to a twig broken from a certain tree, and store the bundle under the roof of his mother's hut" (Nadel, 1947:59).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "Every important phase of the agricultural year is accompanied by some ritual event, which similarly transforms rational motives into supernatural promises. Signals for co-ordinated and well-planned efforts become repeated sacred guarantees against failure and misfortune" (Nadel, 1947:44). See also Nadel, 1947:94-98 for more information on rituals for defining Otoro clan membership.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "These rituals may be of a very specific and detailed nature as in Heiban or in Koalib, where nearly every cultivated plant and every phase of its cultivation have their separate rites, their own priestly experts, and command special magic gestures symbolic of the growth which these rites are meant to ensure" (Nadel, 1947:44).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information on specific extra-ritual in-group markers.

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: "The association of cicatrization with a test of manhood is emphasized in various ways. The very cicatrization pattern is thought of as a symbol of manly virtues. Men who killed an enemy in a fight are entitled to have a small pattern of scars (four to seven rows) cicatrized on their backs" (Nadel, 1947:142).

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: For descriptions of food avoidances, see Nadel, 1947:98-99, 520.

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: "On the next day [in a series of sacrifices and rituals associated with permanent scarring] a sacrifice called nmaro takes place; it repeats the essential features of the previous lortede rite [in which bracelets of skin are cut from a goat and given to the person undergoing the permanent scarring ritual], but also includes the assumption by the dermoco-to-be [person undergoing scarring ritual] of a new emblem of his status, a cowrie necklace, from which this rite takes its name" (Nadel, 1947:142).

Other:

– Yes [specify]: Teeth broken out

Notes: "But first [before gendered labor division] they undergo the same mutilation, the breaking out of the lower front teeth—four in Heiban, two (of boys) or four (of girls) in Otoro" (Nadel, 1947:132).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community, the Otoro have one level of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a petty chiefdom (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 32).

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: "But it [preventing the accumulation of wealth] also renders the food economy of the tribe most vulnerable. It prevents any effective insurance against the perennial risks of locusts, droughts, or failures of the crops. It is not surprising, then, that famines visit the Nuba hills with sinister regularity" (Nadel, 1947:49).

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "In the event of famine, the [British] Government intervenes with emergency measures" (Nadel, 1947:50).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of formal education provided by the religious group.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: See Nadel, 1947:86 for a map of the Otoro Hills and location of the [British] Government School. However, the principle ethnographic authority (Nadel, 1947) did not specify whether the Otoro attended the Government School.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The Otoro Nuba were under British rule at the time of the writing of principle ethnographic authority (Nadel, 1947).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food was stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food was stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that scarcity in the water supply and the absence of water management has limited expansion of the Nuba into new territory (Nadel, 1947:27).

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of water management provided by another

institution.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– I don't know

Notes: It is not clear whether the Otoro or the British government levy taxes: "Centralized control, itself unprecedented in most of these strongly segmented societies, was rendered even more precarious when charged with the modern administrative duties of tax-collection, the recruiting of labour for public work, or the prosecution of offenders." (Nadel, 1947:494-495).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 90, Police, police functions are not specialized (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Ethnographic evidence indicates that there is no institutional law enforcement present: "The law is enforced, not by the actions of an appointed authority, but by public approval of 'self-help'; and 'law and order' often covers only a small segment of social life" (Nadel, 1947:146).

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the Nuba interacted with and participated in an institutionalized police force provided by the British government: "The people are well aware that behind the individual agents of the [British] Government, behind Mufettish, Mamur, policeman or chief, there is a supreme, abstract entity—the Hakuma [Arabic for government]" (Nadel, 1947:497). "It is the Nuba tradition of manliness that has led so many of them to serve in the Army and the police, and to contribute so notably to the military traditions of the Sudan" (Nadel, 1947:xii).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: See Nadel, 1947:161 for a description of the Native and Tribal Courts, as well as Nadel, 1947:127, 159 for examples of cases seen by the Native Court.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "Homicide is dealt with, not by the Native Court, but, after a magisterial inquiry, by the judge of the [British] High Court" (Nadel, 1947:160).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "Similarly, sub-chiefs may hear local cases in their own hills and villages, though the sentences which they pass must be confirmed by the higher tribal or federal court" (Nadel, 1947:161).

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: Sentences of execution are not made by the Native Courts: "Homicide is dealt with, not by the Native Court, but, after a magisterial inquiry, by the judge of the High Court. We are interested here only in the relation of the sentences passed by the High Court—long-term imprisonment or death—with the traditional legal concepts" (Nadel, 1947:160).

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: See Nadel, 1947:151 for description of circumstances surrounding ostracism.

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: "The owner of the animals would complain to the chief, who would summon the thief and order him to restore what he had stolen. Should the thief ignore the summons—as he might if he thought himself strong enough to reject this interference—the chief would enlist the help of every man on whom he could rely, attack the offender and strip him and those who dared to come to his aid of all their possessions" (Nadel, 1947:151).

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "Homicide is dealt with, not by the Native Court, but, after a magisterial inquiry, by the judge of the High Court. We are interested here only in the relation of the sentences passed by the High Court—long-term imprisonment or death—with the traditional legal concepts" (Nadel, 1947:160).

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: "Homicide is dealt with, not by the Native Court, but, after a magisterial inquiry, by the judge of the High Court. We are interested here only in the relation of the sentences passed by the High Court—long-term imprisonment or death—with the traditional legal concepts" (Nadel, 1947:160).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Because the society possesses formal Native and Tribal Courts, it can be assumed that a formal legal code is also present (Nadel, 1947:127).

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Because the society is subject to the formal Sudanese judicial and police systems, it can be assumed that a formal legal code is also present (Nadel, 1947:160, 497).

Warfare

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the Nuba generally participated in the military, which is assumed to include the Otoro: "It is the Nuba tradition of manliness that has led so many of them to serve in the [British] Army and the police, and to contribute so notably to the military traditions of the Sudan" (Nadel, 1947:xii).

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: "Not until public security was finally established under British rule and raids by Arabs or neighbouring hill tribes had ceased, did the Nuba farmer feel safe out in the open, unprotected plain" (Nadel, 1947:16).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1 [of Cultural Complexity] - Writing and Records, mnemonic devices are utilized, but no writing or records specific to the religious group (Murdock and Provost, 1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "In electing their modern chiefs or sub-chiefs, the people look for qualifications of a new kind: knowledge of Arabic, acquaintance with the ways of the Hakuma [Arabic for government], an energetic temperament, and suitable age for undertaking the new tasks of office, like tax-collection, recruiting labour for road work . . ." (Nadel, 1947:164-165).

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "In electing their modern chiefs or sub-chiefs, the people look for qualifications of a new kind: knowledge of Arabic, acquaintance with the ways of the Hakuma [Arabic for government], an energetic temperament, and suitable age for undertaking the new tasks of office, like tax-collection, recruiting labour for road work . . ." (Nadel, 1947:164-165).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: For description of the tribal calendar, see Nadel, 1947:44-45.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society itself, this entry assumes that the religious group provides food for themselves. The Otoro Nuba depend primarily on intensive agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) and pastoralism (SCCS Variable 206, Dependence on Animal Husbandry) as secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Pastoralism

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society itself, this entry assumes that the religious group provides food for themselves. The Otoro Nuba depend primarily on intensive agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) and pastoralism (SCCS Variable 206, Dependence on Animal Husbandry) as secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 7 and 28).